

PARENTAL RESILIENCE: A PHENOMENOLOGICAL STUDY ON MOTHERS NURTURING CHILDREN 3 - 6 YEARS OLD WITH MENTAL HEALTH NEEDS

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ABSTRACT

Parental resilience is crucial for children's overall development, especially in stressful situations. This study explores the experiences of mothers raising young children with mental health needs, focusing on the importance of mental health for overall well-being. The research, conducted using purposive and snowballing techniques, interviewed six mothers whose children aged 3-6 have mental health needs. The findings reveal that mothers' parenting is influenced by their acceptance of their children's disabilities and their knowledge about these conditions. Physical and mental well-being support for their children is emphasized, involving adherence to prescribed treatments and effective communication. The study also highlights the challenges faced by mothers, including financial constraints, adapting to a new normal due to medical challenges, and navigating educational challenges. Active listening to children's concerns is vital for their psychological security. The study recommends a collaborative educational approach, leveraging the experiences of mothers and teachers to design individualized support systems, fortifying parental resilience, and enhancing children's physical security during their developmental years. The study aims to understand the experiences of mothers in nurturing young children with mental health needs and how this can be applied to create a program that provides psychological security for children.

Keywords: *Parental resilience, Mental Health Needs, Well-being, Psychological Security, Child Development*

INTRODUCTION

This study focuses on the experiences of mothers nurturing children with mental health needs.

Up to 20% of children worldwide suffer from debilitating mental illnesses, including learning disorders, ADHD, depression, psychosis, developmental disorders, attachment disorders, anxiety disorders, conduct disorders, substance abuse, and eating disorders. Living with such children can be extremely stressful for family caregivers, and professional assistance, public awareness of mental illnesses in children, and social and financial support from the government, private sector, and NGOs are critical in addressing these challenges. (Ambikile & Outwater, 2012; Nikolaev et al., 2016).

Parental resilience is defined as a parent's internal resources and coping skills that assist them in dealing with stress and crises. Resilient coping skills enable a parent to solve problems, remain calm and collected when upset, and persevere during difficult times. Parental resilience plays an important role in the overall development of children, especially in stressful situations or circumstances. (Gmuca et al., 2019; Gavidia-Payne et al., 2015).

Mental health problems in young children manifest as emotional and behavioral disorders and are closely related to the negative factors of a discordant family environment for the child. A mother's maladaptive coping styles play a significant role in the formation of a discordant family. The findings suggest that mothers' coping patterns, in conjunction with their parenting styles, play a dysfunctional role in their children's mental health.

Co-occurring medical conditions are very common in children with autism spectrum disorder (ASD), and these conditions include speech, sleep, and gastrointestinal issues (including constipation and feeding problems), developmental delay, attention deficit/hyperactivity disorder, hypotonia, epilepsy, anxiety, disruptive behavior, pica, and eczema.

Several psychiatric disorders, particularly neurodevelopmental disorders, such as autism spectrum disorder (ASD), have been known to be interrelated with other medical conditions. To help in battling mental health concerns, it is essential to start at the roots and prioritize their mental health among other aspects of Early Childhood Development. This study aims to understand and explore the experiences of mothers in nurturing young children ages three to six and gearing them towards mental health, particularly mothers of children with mild to moderate psychosocial disabilities.

Research Questions

This study aims to explore the experiences of mothers in nurturing young children aged three to six, particularly those with mental health needs, and how this can be applied to create a program that provides psychological security for children.

Specifically, this study aims to answer the following questions:

1. What are the experiences of mothers in terms of nurturing young children with mental health needs?
2. What are the struggles and challenges faced while nurturing young children with mental health needs?
3. What possible proposed health information dissemination scheme related to mental health can be established for Montessori pupils?

The study emphasizes the importance of focusing on the overall development of children during the early years, particularly in mental health.

METHODOLOGY

This qualitative descriptive study aimed to understand the experiences of mothers in nurturing young children aged three to six and focusing on mental health for children with mental health needs. The research methodology used included a phenomenological, descriptive, and qualitative approach. Phenomenological research is commonly used in nursing research methodology to understand human research. The study aimed to explore the experiences of mothers in terms of nurturing their children, particularly those with mild to moderate mental health needs.

The researcher used a mixture of purposive sampling and snowballing techniques to identify participants. Participants were mothers aged 23 years or older, who had children aged 3 to 6 years with mild to moderate disabilities related to psychosocial, learning, or chronic illnesses. The mothers were the primary caregivers for their children.

Inclusion criteria included mothers aged 23 years or older with children with mild to moderate disabilities related to psychosocial, learning, or chronic illnesses. The guidance office of the school aided in identifying these students based on readily available information. An assessment based on the World Health Organization Disability Assessment Schedule 2.0 (WHODAS 2.0) and Parent/Guardian Rated DSM-5 Level 1 Cross-Cutting Symptom Measure-Child Aged 6–17 questionnaires was used to assess whether the participants were included in the study.

Ethics and Human Rights Considerations were also considered in the research. The study aimed to provide additional information and resources, raise awareness about providing

long-term support and care for children's mental health and psychological security, and provide a comprehensive understanding of maternal nurturing experiences.

The study involved a pilot study to test the validity and reliability of interview questions. After obtaining permission from the partnered school, the researcher identified probable respondents based on set assessment criteria and gave informed consent. The researcher and respondents agreed on a time and schedule at their convenience for the interview after signing the consent form. Both face to face and google meet interview was provided as an option for the respondents. The interview lasted approximately 30 minutes to 1 hour, and the researcher confirmed whether the information provided was the same as the notes written during the interview.

Strategies to improve communication were used. Some participants opted to have someone accompany them in case they felt uncomfortable conducting the interview alone. Clarifications and probing questions were asked to ensure all information stated was factual and understood correctly. Due to the probable distress experienced by the respondents, a mental health professional was partnered with for debriefing after the interview had concluded.

Data was analysed according to the chosen method and disposed of appropriately through shredding physical paper notes used during the interview phase. Digital copies of recordings were deleted after collation and analysis, and no data collected and stored on a secure hard drive will be stored for more than one year after publication.

RESULTS

The researcher used Colaizzi's Method of Data Analysis to analyze data, uncovering essential themes and patterns. The findings provide insights into mothers' experiences in nurturing their children's mental health needs. The data was thoroughly read, offering insights into challenges, emotions, and perspectives. Significant statements were identified, capturing essential aspects of the respondents' experiences.

Theme I: Shaping Parenting

One's experiences have a profound effect on how they raise or parent their children. dividing the process of forming a parent's approach into two phases: first, accepting the disability (e.g., learning about the disease for the first time) and second, their understanding of the impairment (e.g., what they know then and now).

Subtheme #1: Coming to terms with the disability.

Accepting the disability—which is primarily addressed in the medical context—by first identifying the symptoms and learning about the ailment. The type and specific

manifestations of the children's disability determined the degree of recognition. Recognition occurred in response to advice from others in certain circumstances, and in other cases it was tinged with uncertainty due to a lack of trust in the diagnosis. Others emerged as a result of their own observation of specific indicators, which led them to take action. Certain disorders took longer to recognize than others, such as learning disabilities and health issues that presented as symptoms that people thought were typical. Other accounts did not initially understand what normal development included, which is why they took longer to recognize the handicap. Despite being aware that something was amiss, others choose not to consider the possibility that something might be off. In contrast, there were accounts which detailed their recognition of their child's disability based on what they know about development while others attribute the recognition of their son's disability to the oddities that she noticed and the shared experiences of other parents:

Respondent 1: He was an active boy, he loved to play around with the neighbour's so when we slept and he started snoring, I just thought "Ah he enjoyed his day playing with his friends". I did not think a lot about it.

Respondent 4: My son did not start speaking at two, his sister started early, but that still did not give me a lot of concern since he still has time, my brother did not start to speak until later.

Respondent 3: "I was always with my daughter; I bring her to daycare and stay with her until the session for the day is over. Once I brought her to a school, the moment I said bye, she would start crying and I end up staying near her room where she can see me. This went on for a while. I did not think much of it I just thought it was because she was a mama's girl."

Respondent 5: "So at 2 years old, I started to notice different signs that there was something wrong. So I talked to others about it, sharing inputs on whether or not I should be worried. His communication was delayed, and he was diagnosed with global developmental delay." While Mother 6 mentioned "So, we found out early on that there was something wrong with him. He was diagnosed with Global Developmental Delay, and Autism at 2 years old."

Subtheme #2: knowledge on the disability

When parents found out about their children's disabilities, their acceptance of it was based more on their understanding of the mental, emotional, and practical aspects of accepting the condition. The degree of information they possessed at the time of the diagnosis was primarily dependent on the reason why and how they happened to be concerned having them checked out. When it comes to helping moms accept the disabilities of their children, education plays a crucial role in influencing how they meet their needs on a physical and, more significantly, mental level. To effectively deal with the needs of children with mental health difficulties, providing care for them requires a certain level of proficiency (Hoogsteyns et al., 2023). Sometimes, especially with complicated medical conditions (such as tumours or chronic diseases), experts are quick to diagnose, but parents are

cautious to follow their advice. Many of them have admitted to obtaining consultation by calling upon a hospital in a different city for a second opinion.

Respondent 1 (Mother of a boy with a congenitally enlarged tonsils).

At the time that we found out about it, we did not really know what to feel about it. We were confused and scared about the prospect of him having a tumour. Honestly, at that time, we did not know that his snoring would lead to something like this. The only thing we knew about his illness was what the doctor explained. We tried to do research through Google to ease our worries, but it only made the worrying worse because there was a large variation of causes and probable reasons why that happened and that made me overthink that things might get worse.

We decided that before we even did something about it, we would have a second opinion elsewhere. We were bound to transfer to Cebu because of my husband. So, we decided that we would have him checked up here.

Respondent 4 (Mother of a boy with Dyslexia)

Before we found out about his dyslexia, he was a sickly kid. He had fever that would last days and are always high. We did not know what it was he was still an infant. We had him checked in our local hospital and the doctor said he had Kawasaki Disease. We did not know what it was, so before we decided to get him treated, we went to another city to have him checked to get a second opinion.

Respondent (mother of a boy with Autism Spectrum Disorder, Social Communication Disorder and G6PD Deficiency)

I did my own research by reading on research articles, attending seminars for parents of children with ASD.

Respondent (mother of a boy with autism spectrum disorder and Epilepsy)

The things we mainly did were getting advice from friends who also have children with ASD, but then every child with ASD is so different that even though they're the same in terms of diagnosis, their development can vary from one case to the next. Therapy wise, we also took to research, reading articles, about different treatment options.

Emerging Theme #2: Supporting their Children's Well-Being

Managing a disability may lead to a great deal of stress to both the child needing care and the nurturing mother. Children naturally seek to advance toward higher levels of psychosocial maturity as they grow older (Deci and Ryan 2000). To aid in their psychological development, parents can support the needs of their kids for relatedness, competence, and autonomy (Soenens et al., 2017). a hospital in a different city.

Subtheme #1: Physical Support

A child's physical well-being is something that is always given priority: their health. A mother's top priority is ensuring that her children have enough food and sleep. especially for children who require mental health support. distinct needs accompany distinct infirmities.

Respondent 1 and 2 concentrated on ensuring that all medical needs (such as medications) and physical activity based on medically founded advice are met; Respondent 6 highlighted the value of therapy for their children's physical support; v 5 stressed the significance of playtime; and v 4 believes that his son's pickiness is due to the food he was given when he was younger.

Respondent 1: We just followed what his doctor instructed us to do. The aftercare of the wound, the medicines he needs. Now, I support his physical well-being through encouraging his physical activity and encouraging him to eat a healthy diet. I make sure that he drinks his vitamins, he eats his vegetables and drinks his medicine. While he is still little, I want to encourage him to play outside more for physical activity.

Respondent 2: I make sure that he drinks his vitamins, he eats his vegetables and drinks his medicine. While he is still little, I want to encourage him to play outside more for physical activity.

Respondent 6: Apart from speech therapy, my son has occupational therapy, and until now he is on that therapy religiously. You can see some improvement in him in terms of his physique but there is still a long way to go. We do understand because he is on medication that can increase his appetite, he is a relatively big boy. So as much as possible, for us, any time physical activity through therapy is done, we really take an advantage of that for his sake.

Respondent 5: Playtime for us is important, especially for kuya, apart from his therapies, one of the more hands on approached we had to make sure that he gets some sort of physical activity is playtime, when he was younger through toys, now, we do encourage him from time to time to play basketball with his dad.

Respondent 4: When we started him on more solid foods, the first thing we introduced to him were apples, mangoes, chicken. As he grew, the food that he it's are more predictable, does not like anything that he is not familiar with. He likes fruits but cannot stand avocados, he does not like sweets, and would choose bread over cake, or ice cream. That was something that shocked us a bit because a lot of kids, you think they like candies, but him, he really does not like it.

Respondent 6: My son has epilepsy apart from ASD so because he has epilepsy, he has certain meds which make him hungry so most of the time he loves to eat. He does not like durian, he hates it. He also does not like animal insides any, intestines, liver, brain. He does not like the smell of both especially. He loves adobo, anything if its adobo, it can be chicken or pork. He is okay with fruits; he is also okay with vegetables. The most

important to me is for him to be able to have a balanced meal, so I make sure that when he eats, he also eats smart.

Subtheme #2: Mental and Emotional Support

As a child grows physically, they encounter new challenges that can either strengthen or weaken their sense of self. Fostering the physical development of young children contributes to their overall success (Maybery et al., 2005). This study aims to investigate how moms provide for their children who have mental health difficulties. This can take the shape of physical illnesses, learning challenges, or psychosocial disabilities, all of which have a big influence on how their kids grow up and their long-term psychological stability.

Respondent 1: I listen to him and his concerns, I go with him to his check-ups and encourage him to talk to me if he feels sad and overwhelmed.

Respondent 6: Apart from all the physical aspects, the therapy, the medications, the importance of physical activity and stimulation. It is for us ensuring that we get to make him understand that we do care for him. It is to make sure that he can take care of himself and learn to be more independent.

Frustration, fatigue, and other emotions might arise during mother-child interactions because of the difficulties these children deal with daily as a result of their disability. These children may be deficient in certain areas, but their senses are sharper in others. These children have a high degree of emotional sensitivity. They are capable of processing emotions since, even if they are unable to articulate it in a way that others can comprehend.

When a child speaks, they communicate what they want you to understand; however, they are not always easily understood (De Schauwer et al., 2023). The significance of listening guarantees individuals' security and confidence that they are heard. They feel more secure knowing that, from a certain viewpoint, everything will work out. According to the respondents' testimonies, they make sure children are aware that they will always receive help when they need it.

Respondent 3: I always tell her that we are always there for her, but at the same time she has to learn and understand that we will not always be physically present.

Respondent 4: I can say that it is not that easy, you really need to be patient with him, and you must make him feel that you are supportive of him. He can sense just by looking at you that something is wrong, and it makes him frustrated.

Respondent 5: One thing that I really learned from taking care of him is that you should not let them know that you are tired. Even if you say "A gikapoy nako" (I am tired) he will know. He is a very sensitive child, and he is very sensitive to emotional cues so he will understand that you feel tired and that it is because of him, so you should not let them know that you are tired.

Some children struggle more than others, and this might end up becoming a weakness. Due to their perceived uniqueness, individuals fall prey to many forms of mistreatment, such as bullying. Many of the respondents strive to ensure that their children realize that bullying constitutes offense, and they should learn how to protect themselves and gain self-reliance abilities.

Respondent 5: The most important thing for me is to make sure that he can learn to become independent and equip him with the necessary social and the basic skills. It is also important for us that he learns to defend himself because he will be bullied, and it will not be the only time, and it is not always that he will have someone to protect him.

Mothers' collective experiences have influenced the way they address the mental health needs of their children. Some mothers clarify that there are some things that parents need to be aware of before approaching their kids. By doing this, you may establish parameters with their children.

Respondent 5: There are 6 things that I always tell people especially for those who do not know him or those who just met him. ... I tell them these things because (1) they really have to know that you cannot do this with them I am setting boundaries, (2) there is a tendency that you will not get along (3) you might get hurt, and (4) it is quite obvious that there would be differences between you and me and him and you, and not everyone knows how to approach him when something happens or just want to get to know him.

Respondent 6: The challenges are changing, but there are daily struggles that remain the same. When I get asked about what the struggles are when it comes to taking care of him, I always mention more or less 4 things. I tell this to people not to discourage them but to explain to them and just to answer their questions. There are times that my son can be manipulative in a way. So, I just want to explain to people especially his teacher now, that there are things that he does, a he does it to get a reaction out of you. Once he gets that reaction from you, he is satisfied.

Emerging theme #3: Living with Children's Disabilities.

Each participant in this research has a different background; there are mothers who work, mothers who remain at home with their children, and women who work part-time. Despite the disparities in their histories, they all express the same feeling, which is that their experiences with their children's disabilities transformed their lives beyond the early period of their diagnosis.

Subtheme #1: Financial Challenges

The first of many difficulties these moms have encountered in raising their children is running out of money and resources to ensure that their child receives the best care possible. Some employ alternative methods, such as quitting their job completely and having their spouse cover their expenses to make sure their children are properly taken care of. Others have made the decision to look for a different, more flexible career to care

for their child and yet work to make ends meet. These moms disclosed that their usual expenses are getting higher and finances became tighter.

Respondent 4: The biggest challenge we had was our finances. Since he was admitted, to his check-ups, to the medications. It got to a point where we would borrow money from my sister, and other relatives, we exhausted a lot of loans because of it. Now, because he is enrolled in a public school, our educational expenses are not that high but because of our financial difficulties, we are still trying to get it all together.

Respondent 5: Both me and my husband were working, but we both wanted to make sure that he was taken care of, that his therapies were done. Sacrifices had to be made, my son was 4 years old when I decided to retire from my job and permanently take care of him. I would take him to therapy, I would take him to school and fetch him, and once he got home instead of encouraging television, I encouraged him to play with toys more.

Respondent 6: When our son was younger, I was still able to work and take care of my son when I get home. We also hired a *yaya* that would take care of the kids when we were at work and would come home when we arrived. As he grew, it was growing difficult having to take him to his therapies, and holding a job that requires my physical presence. So I decided to quit the job that I had and look for another work which I could stay at home and work at the same time so I could take care of him. Financially, because of the therapies for all the conditions, because of the medications he is on, the expenses are pretty high, and we cannot avoid it, since it is a given because these treatments are expensive. Apart from that he has 2 other siblings so the budget is pretty tight, but sacrifices have to be made. I have to work and so does my husband. We have a *yaya* that works with us part time, most of the time takes care of the other children and the house.

Subtheme #2: Medical Challenges

The change in their concept of normal is the second adjustment that these women need to get used to. The numerous therapies, the frequent trips to the doctor, the medical advice, the prescription drugs, and so much more. Mothers are encountering challenges when navigating the healthcare system that has increased their financial strain.

Parents start to worry about their children in unfamiliar surroundings, when they are not there, and what would happen to them if no one knew what to do in the instance of a child emergency.

Another describes the psychological difficulties brought on by surgical operations, the scars they leave behind, and the physical and emotional effects on their kid.

Respondent 2: After the surgery, he had a difficult time voiding properly, he does not have full control of his bowel movement. Apart from that he has a huge scar in his stomach area. He became insecure of showing of his scar because according to him it looked like his butt. Apart from that, he still has trouble controlling his bowel movement so there is still a big risk that he could poop himself in school and people would tease him about it.

She went on to explain I always told him that if ever that happened, I was one phone call away. I always made sure that he always had extras in his bag incase that happened.

Respondent 2: We live far from the city; the hospitals are in the center. We do not have a car to transport us. The travel time takes so long that in case of an emergency it would be better at times to commute there. But that is not realistic at all. We need an ambulance to get us there, but even the ambulance with the newer equipment are in the city, and those that are farther don't have those. What are we supposed to do when something so urgent would happen?

Respondent 4: When we had him checked in the local hospital and were told that it might be Kawasaki Disease. We were extremely worried because we did not know what that was, we did not know how severe it would be, how it would affect him. We were shocked as to how they were able to determine it so quick. We feel like we are being scammed because we had little knowledge about the disease.

Respondent 6: The main struggle in all of this especially right now is his epilepsy, so he does have his medication, and we make sure that he does take these meds. But there is always that constant fear that he might have a seizure and we are not there and that the people around him don't know what to do. So we really want to ensure his safety above everything else.

Subtheme #3: Educational Challenges

Regardless of whether their child has a disability, many parents believe that education is crucial. For parents of children with disabilities (CWD), this is especially true. But there are additional difficulties associated with sending their child to school. There are those in the educational system who can handle the rigors of a traditional education as well as individuals who couldn't. Concerns should also be raised about the child's capacity to interact with other kids and the degree of their disabilities. Education sometimes entails therapy for those with impairments, which can add to the family's financial burden adding to the cost of education, which is already high.

Respondent 4: Because he has dyslexia, he has difficulty when it comes to his studies, especially in English, he still has difficulty in his alphabets, his b's and d's are exchanged, his p's are inverted. There are times that he would be frustrated because we could not understand what he was trying to say and because of that he would cause tantrums.

Respondent 5: Education wise, before he was being transferred from private school to public school in SPED because he was having trouble coping with the demands of regular classes. The pandemic did alter the way we approached things. Both me and my husband became more hands on, which honestly helped a lot. Now, he can cope with some but not all of the demands of regular class since we started to blend him with other kids. But we are introducing it to him slowly because we do not want to overwhelm him.

Respondent 6: The challenges are changing, but there are struggles that remain the same. So education wise, because my son has difficulty speaking, he is undergoing speech therapy, and occupational therapy there are a lot of barriers that might be in place, add in the epilepsy. Communicating with him is difficult so some special teaching methods need to be put in place.

Subtheme #4: Social Challenges

The study also revealed a topic that is strongly tied to educational challenges such as the occurrence of stigma, prejudice, and bullying against their children. Bullying is a problem that should be taken seriously, particularly if you have children with disabilities. As a result, mothers prioritize teaching their children how to defend themselves from bullies. The child's well-being is a reflection of the mother's love and care for them. Despite the challenges they may face in their various roles, most moms of children with mental health concerns want to continue instilling positive attitudes in their children.

Respondent 5: Bullying was really something that he struggled on since he started schooling because there were kids, some even older than him that would tease him, laugh at him, the worst was when he went to the bathroom and one of the kids playfully said that "hala ga linog" while he was peeing, so he ended up with wet pants. Which made me furious. It was a good thing that one of his classmates was there and told the teacher immediately. That was one of the reasons we switched him from private to public.

Respondent 6: The biggest fear we have is that we would be bullied, belittled because he is non-verbal so he cannot protect himself, and at the moment he heavily relies on us. So we really do have to teach him independence and to be patient with him.

Respondent 2: Because he is always absent and rather sickly, he is thin, and there have been times that he was called names like "tukog" or "masakiton." Because of this we were concerned that he would take it personally and it would hurt him to the point that he might become discouraged. It was painful to hear children calling him names because he was sickly. On my side, it has been difficult because other people who are not really that close to us, always say that I did not take care of him that well because he always ended up in the hospital because of some sort of illness.

Respondent 5: incident I always tell him "Kuya if possible, you pee at home and not in school so you can avoid it happening again, if you really have to go, then use the close toilet." Aside from that reminder, I always tell him that he should not initiate anything unless someone does it first. If someone hits you hit back, and only when it is necessary. To me it is more important to make sure that he can protect himself.

Subtheme #5: Mental Health Challenges

From the standpoint of a caregiver, in addition to all other challenges, the mothers also face the toll in caring for children with mental health needs as it takes on their own mental

health however, others, opted to focus on the brighter aspects of things while still admitting that there are difficulties inherent situation.

Respondent 4: It is physically, emotionally, and financially exhausting. You really need to have patience you must be able to in a way take a punch because, you must handle frustrations well. You have to make sure that you are helping him progress forward in the best possible way.

Respondent 5: It is draining in a lot of ways, it is mentally, physically draining to take care of him, but seeing the progress, it is honestly really rewarding. We had a lot of struggles with him from the moment we found out. The therapies are expensive. From a financial standpoint, there were challenges.

Emerging Theme #4: The Role of Support

The psychological well-being of the caregiver for the child that has mental health needs could be undermined because of attending to their needs. To remain strong for their children, parents, especially mothers, need the assistance of others. Support is provided by family members and other well-meaning individuals. Others even through prayers and spiritual support. Particularly in Filipino culture, the idea of a "bayanihan," or helping hand, is not new and encompasses all challenges that someone may encounter. They are also closer because of the support system that families provide.

Respondent 1: There has been people who have supported me from the moment that my son was diagnosed up until now. These were mothers who also had children admitted, the mothers of children admitted in the same ward as my son during my son’s operation and recovery, mothers of my son’s classmates and my neighbors. Because they helped me so much during my time of difficulty, I think it is now my turn to support them if they ever needed help.

Respondent 4: At that time my sister really came through and helped me especially with the finances. I got to save on transportation because she would take me and my son. My daughter, my sons ate also stepped up and took care of their little brother, while we focused on him. My mother-in-law also stepped-in and took care of the house, the children while we had away and really helped us anyway, she could.

Significant Statements	Formulated Meanings	Cluster themes
<i>He was an active boy, he loved to play around with the neighbor’s so when we slept and he started snoring, I just thought “Ah he enjoyed his day playing with his friends”. I did not think a lot about it.</i>	Defined the symptoms of his son’s condition to normal human body reaction to becoming tired	Recognition of Illness and its signs

<p><i>My son did not start speaking at two, his sister started early, but that still did not give me a lot of concern since he still has time, my brother did not start to speak until later.</i></p>	<p>Association of symptoms to normal delay in development</p>	
<p><i>I was always with my daughter; I bring her to daycare and stay with her until the session for the day is over. Once I brought her to a school, the moment I said bye, she would start crying and I end up staying near her room where she can see me. This went on for a while. I did not think much of it I just thought it was because she was a mama's girl.</i></p>	<p>Association of concern to maternal bond</p>	
<p><i>So, at 2 years old, I started to notice different signs that there was something wrong. So, I talked to others about it, sharing inputs on whether or not I should be worried. His communication was delayed, and he was diagnosed with global developmental delay.</i></p>	<p>Early recognition attributed to experiences from other parents regarding development</p>	
<p><i>So, we found out early on that there was something wrong with him. He was diagnosed with Global Developmental Delay, and Autism at 2 years old.</i></p>	<p>Early recognition of signs of illness</p>	
<p><i>He was aggressive, my son, he displayed it with anyone, at first we were in denial, my sister-in-law, recognized it immediately, he was visibly showing signs of aggression, but we honestly thought it was just because there was something that was not to his liking</i></p>	<p>In denial, despite recognition of illness</p>	
<p><i>At the time that we found out about it, we did not really know what to feel about it. We were confused and scared about the prospect of him having a tumor. Honestly, at that time, we did not know that his snoring would lead to something like this. We decided that before we even did something about it, we would have a second opinion elsewhere. We were bound to transfer to Cebu because of my husband. So, we decided that we would have him checked up here.</i></p>	<p>To gain further sense of security, second opinion was sought</p>	<p>Knowledge on Illness/ Disorder</p>
<p><i>Before we found out about his dyslexia, he was a sickly kid. He had a fever that would last days and is always high. We did not know what it was when</i></p>	<p>Sought second opinion due to lack of knowledge on illness</p>	

<i>he was still an infant. We had him checked in our local hospital and the doctor said he had Kawasaki Disease. We did not know what it was, so before we decided to get him treated, we went to another city to have him checked to get a second opinion.</i>		
<i>I did my own research by reading on research articles, attending seminars for parents of children with ASD.</i>	Researching on the disorder and its different treatments	
<i>The things we mainly did were getting advice from friends who also have children with ASD, but then every child with ASD is so different that even though their the same in terms of diagnosis, their development can vary from one case to the next. Therapy wise, we also took to research, reading articles, about different treatment options.</i>	Researching on the disorder along with information from other parents with the same disorder.	
<i>My son both had behavioral and speech therapy. He was aggressive, we were in denial. When he was diagnosed at 3 years old, we were scared, because of the stigma associated with that was all we knew about. We had to have research, for a time after the diagnosis we had to home school him. He just started going to school so we had to make sure he can be well adjusted</i>	Stigma present in association with illness and the knowledge of it.	
<i>We just followed what his doctor instructed us to do. The aftercare of the wound, the medicines he needs. Now, I support his physical well-being through encouraging his physical activity and encouraging him to eat a healthy diet.</i>	Medical Treatment, vital in physical support	Different types of physical support
<i>I make sure that he drinks his vitamins, he eats his vegetables and drinks his medicine. While he is still little, I want to encourage him to play outside more for physical activity.</i>	Importance of Supplementation	
<i>Apart from speech therapy, my son has occupational therapy, and until now he is on that therapy religiously. You can see some improvement in him in terms of his physique but there is still a long way to go. We do understand because he is on medication that can increase his appetite, he is a relatively big boy. So as much as possible, for us, any time physical activity through therapy is done, we really take advantage of that for his sake.</i>	Importance of therapy in physical activity	
<i>My son has epilepsy apart from ASD so because he has epilepsy, he has certain meds which make him hungry so most of the time he loves to eat. He does not like durian, he hates it. He also does not</i>	The Role of food in supplementing needed nutrients	

<i>like animal insides any, intestines, liver, brain. He does not like the smell of both especially. He loves adobo, anything if its adobo, it can be chicken or pork. He is okay with fruits; he is also okay with vegetables. The most important thing to me is for him to be able to have a balanced meal, so I make sure that when he also eats smart.</i>		
<i>I listen to him and his concerns, I go with him to his check-ups and encourage him to talk to me if he feels sad and overwhelmed.</i>	Listening and Reassuring	Different Types of Mental Support
<i>I always tell her that we are always there for her, but at the same time she has to learn and understand that we will not always be physically present.</i>	Reassurance as a key part of support	
<i>The most important thing for me is to make sure that he can learn to become independent and equip him with the necessary social and basic skills. It is also important for us that he learns to defend himself because he will be bullied, and it will not be the only time, and it is not always that he will have someone to protect him.</i>	Teaching independence and protection from certain social situations	
<i>Apart from all the physical aspects, the therapy, the medications, the importance of physical activity and stimulation. It is for us to ensure that we get to make him understand that we do care for him. It is to make sure that he can take care of himself and learn to be more independent.</i>	Making their children understand that they will always be there for them	
<i>We, both his father and I, are in the field of science. His brother is a marine biologist, so he gets along with him well in comparison to our youngest. We noticed he is less aggressive when we show him marine related docuseries and things related to marine life. So most often, we take him Ocean Park a lot.</i>	Identifying their likes and using them as calming factors	
<i>The biggest challenge we had was our finances. Since he was admitted, to his check-ups, to the medications. It got to a point where we would borrow money from my sister, and other relatives, we exhausted a lot of loans because of it. Now, because he is enrolled in a public school, our educational expenses are not that high but because of our financial difficulties, we are still trying to get it all together.</i>	Financial Exhaustion due to medical related expenses	Financial Challenges experienced by mothers
<i>Both me and my husband were working, but we both wanted to make sure that he was taken care of, that his therapies were done. Sacrifices had to</i>	Leaving their jobs to provide more hands-on care	

<p><i>be made, my son was 4 years old when I decided to retire from my job and permanently take care of him. I would take him to therapy, I would take him to school and fetch him, and once he got home instead of encouraging him to watch television, I encouraged him to play with toys more.</i></p>		
<p><i>When our son was younger, I was still able to work and take care of my son when I got home. We also hired a yaya that would take care of the kids when we were at work and would come home when we arrived. As he grew, it was growing difficult having to take him to his therapies, and holding a job that requires my physical presence. So, I decided to quit the job that I had and look for another work which I could stay at home and work at the same time so I could take care of him.</i></p>	<p>Looking for other jobs which enable them to earn and provide hands on care</p>	
<p><i>Um, honestly, from a financial standpoint it is very difficult. Having to spend money for his therapies on top of his other needs. Both me and my husband must work, but my husband is pulling more weight than I am since I wanted to be more hands on.</i></p>	<p>Having a balance between work and care for their child</p>	
<p><i>We live far from the city; the hospitals are in the center. We do not have a car to transport us. The travel time takes so long that in case of an emergency it would be better at times to commute there. But that is not realistic at all. We need an ambulance to get us there, but even the ambulance with the newer equipment is in the city, and those that are farther don't have those. What are we supposed to do when something so urgent happens?</i></p>	<p>The difficulties brought by distance between home and hospital or clinic</p>	<p>Medical Challenges</p>
<p><i>The main struggle in all of this, especially right now is his epilepsy, so he does have his medication, and we make sure that he does take these meds. But there is always that constant fear that he might have a seizure and we are not there and that the people around him don't know what to do. So, we really want to ensure his safety above everything else.</i></p>	<p>The influence of the effects of medication in everyday activities.</p>	
<p><i>Education-wise, before he was being transferred from private school to public school in SPED because he was having trouble coping with the demands of regular classes. The pandemic did alter the way we approached things. Both me and my husband became more hands on, which</i></p>	<p>Difficulty in coping with demands in school</p>	<p>Different Challenges towards their child's education</p>

<p><i>honestly helped a lot. Now, he can cope with some but not all the demands of regular class since we started to blend him with other kids. But we are introducing it to him slowly because we do not want to overwhelm him.</i></p>		
<p><i>We previously enrolled him in regular school prior to the diagnosis, we were in denial that there was something wrong with him, so we thought nothing of it. But then he started becoming aggressive towards teachers and even his classmates. We had no choice but to pull him out of school and have him home schooled in addition to his therapies.</i></p>	<p>Fear of harm to others caused by the condition</p>	
<p><i>Bullying was really something that he struggled on since he started schooling because there were kids, some even older than him that would tease him, laugh at him, the worst was when he went to the bathroom and one of the kids playfully said that “hala ga linog” while he was peeing, so he ended up with wet pants. Which made me furious. It was a good thing that one of his classmates was there and told the teacher immediately. That was one of the reasons we switched him from private to public.</i></p>	<p>Difficulty in comprehending social conditions leading their children more vulnerable to social concerns.</p>	<p>Social Challenges for both mothers and their children</p>
<p><i>The biggest fear we have is that we would be bullied, belittled because he is non-verbal so he cannot protect himself, and at the moment he heavily relies on us. So, we really do have to teach him independence and to be patient with him.</i></p>	<p>Fear of being unable to protect themselves, thus advocating for their independence through teaching</p>	
<p><i>His aggressive nature has started to subside after putting him through therapy, but putting him through regular school, with regular children, sometimes they could not comprehend, with the situation, he ends up becoming the bully in some scenarios because of his aggressive and defensive nature.</i></p>	<p>The symptoms brought by the condition providing difficult decisions in different social concerns</p>	
<p><i>It is physically, emotionally, and financially exhausting. You really need to have patience, you must be able to in a way take a punch because, you must handle frustrations well. You have to make sure that you are helping him progress forward in the best possible way.</i></p>	<p>Physical and mental effects of caring for their children</p>	<p>Mental Toll on Mothers</p>
<p><i>It is draining in a lot of ways, it is mentally, physically draining to take care of him, but seeing the progress, it is honestly really rewarding. We had a lot of struggles with him from the moment we</i></p>	<p>The rewards that come with the equivalent mental toll on the mother</p>	

<i>found out. The therapies are expensive. From a financial standpoint, there were challenges.</i>		
<i>Throughout the early phases up until now, I have been through a lot of emotional roller coasters. It is difficult to have him interact with our youngest because 'mag-sumbagay' sila. We want them to be able to stick together and find comfort in each other they grow older, but it is difficult, and really emotional.</i>	A variation of emotions in comprehending with condition	
<i>Support from family and friends really did help get us through the more difficult times, there will be more, so we must really prepare ourselves for it. Of course, faith and prayers cannot really be excluded from this, especially during the times that he has severe seizures, it is enough to give you quite a big scare, he did end up in the hospital. His recovery really strengthened our faith, and his continued progress really solidifies it for us.</i>	Familial support as the foundation to relationships with others.	
<i>... when it came to healing, to us, especially me and my husband, we are spiritually inclined, so it was also important to us, not just to engage in the medical aspect of healing, that spiritual healing was also present. We had a family retreat there then we did confessions, this was not just for me or my husband but our entire family as well.</i>	The importance of spirituality in coping and handling conditions	The role of different types of support systems in coping
<i>Prayer, family, and friends. These three things are the most important for me. When it came to the understanding and navigating of the entire diagnosis to this very day. These are what got me through. Because it is an emotional roller coaster. It's very difficult to comprehend sometimes how difficult it is for me when it came to his condition.</i>	Relationships with religion and family as significant factors in coping	

DISCUSSION

The parent's perspective highlights the significant hardship associated with having a disability, or in this case, caring for a child with mental health needs. These challenges are not just financial; they also have other causes. This covers the strain that it takes on their bodies physically as well as the emotional toll of having to endure it. However, the experience of disability is first held by the parents; the children do not share this experience until they have interacted with peers, become aware of their own impairment and perceived difference.

According to the lived experiences of mothers caring for children with mental health needs, these events have influenced the way the mothers raise their offspring. Resilience

and the availability of social support are important buffers that can help minimize the detrimental impacts of living with a kid who has mental health problems on their quality of life, according to a research by Migerode et al. (2012). Resilience is what helps families deal with the burdens, which raises the question of why resilience is so important in the field of disability studies. Heiman (2002) defined resilience as "successful adjustment in terms of self-esteem, social support, various aspects of social life, problem-solving, and coping strategies, notions of social integration, interdependence, and close relationships."

Their view of disability, which they frame positively (e.g., as a gift, blessing), is another factor included in the research. This source of resilience mentions a variety of spiritual and/or religious resources. This study's findings are in line with the body of research that links religion and disability, even though the issue of religion was only briefly discussed. "Religious support can be a stable coping strategy used throughout the family life cycle," according to the findings of one research (Bennett et al., 1995; Poston & Turnbull, 1985; Selway & Ashman, 1998) that was based on in-depth interviews with parents of children with developmental disabilities (CWDs). The availability or lack of support networks for overcoming their various obstacles is another aspect. Conversely,

The availability or lack of support networks for overcoming their various obstacles is another aspect. When mothers discussed their difficulties and the isolation they experienced from other mothers—especially those they did not even know personally—they were, on the one hand, at their most vulnerable. However, they expressed gratitude for the assistance they had gotten from others. Others mentioned how they use the assistance they receive from friends, family, and support groups to help others. Multinational literature affirms the benefits of support groups. For example, a mixed-methods research carried out in the United States found that parents who were part of these groups. (Lasco et al., 2017).

The medical implication of a disability is one of the highlighted challenges faced by mothers. Most mothers have implied the relationship between finances and medical concerns. Furthermore, although healthcare related gaps are not the objective of this study, their prominence in the narratives presented by these mothers is worth noting. The disparities between their experiences in the healthcare system seem to stem from different factors, which have not been explored as it is not within the study's scope. It is very telling however, that while articles published by the Department of Health DOH on the health and wellness program for persons with disabilities, acknowledge the various gaps present in the treatment of those with disabilities, there are still little action done and/ or proposed to act upon on this regard (Lasco et al., 2021).

One of the issues that mothers encounter that is often overlooked is the medical implications of their disabilities. Most moms have made reference to the connection between health issues and money. Moreover, it is noteworthy that despite not being the study's focus, healthcare-related disparities are prominently included in the stories these moms tell. Since it is outside the purview of the study, the differences in how they experienced the healthcare system appear to be the result of distinct causes, which have not been investigated. Though the Department of Health's DOH articles on the health and

wellness program for people with disabilities acknowledge the many gaps in the way people with disabilities are treated, it is highly striking that little is being done or suggested to address these gaps. (Lasco et al., 2021).

Conclusions

The purpose of this study was to investigate how mothers' experiences caring for their children with mental health problems influenced the method in which they addressed such needs. This study also sought to comprehend the difficulties that these mothers encountered and how they overcame them to determine the best method to care for their children. This study focused on children with mental health needs, their mental health, and how their mothers' nurturing affects the way these children develop psychological stability. Six mothers of children in Cebu City with mental health issues provided data for the study using a descriptive phenomenological research approach.

The findings of the study herein presented to the order of the specific questions formulated in this study:

1. The respondents of the study showed that the experiences of mothers in caring for their children with mental health needs have shaped their way of parenting. Their pursuit for knowledge to continue to understand how to better tackle their children's growing needs. In addition, the importance of supporting their mental health needs, and how they supported them also emerged. Majority of the mothers spoke about the importance of listening to your children's concerns.
2. The respondents of the study have discussed that living with their children and their difficulties pose many challenges in different aspects which includes financial, medical, educational, social, and Mental Health challenges for the mothers. The importance of support systems was also highlighted in the interview as because of the mental toll that the struggles that they have face cause towards them, a strong support system is one important aspect in terms of ensuring that children's psychological security be secured.
3. From the findings of the study, an information dissemination scheme through means of a poster was created. The contents of the poster included the importance of support for both the mother and the child, what are the most common challenges from 2 different perspectives when caring for children with mental health needs.

The findings of the study suggest that the experience of disability is not only shared between caregiver and the child but with the entire family. The narratives presented by the participants all shared the role of their respective families in the entire process from the moment the child is diagnosed to all the individual struggles: the discrimination they receive to the exhaustion of resources (i.e., financial) is vital to the way they parent their children. The concept of resilience is often mentioned in the way people cope with certain pressures that they face in their lives. This concept is what grounds this study. The

amount of understanding that these mothers have towards their children, their individuality, their strengths and their weakness, are reflective of the way they adapt to the challenges that their needs present.

To meet each child's unique requirements, a more flexible strategy must be devised in terms of both schooling and mental health. According to this study, a child's mental requirements could differ from one child to the next even if they have the same diagnosis, depending on how severe the problem is. From an educational perspective, having a thorough grasp of the variations that these situations provide serves as a basis for guiding instructors in developing customized modes—the core idea of the Montessori Approach. The goal of both personalized teaching and Montessori education is to provide a learning environment that best suits the requirements, developmental stage, and interests of each individual student (Mavrič, 1999).

Finally, through understanding the experience from a maternal perspective, a collaborative approach to care between parents and their teachers, especially for those children with mental health needs, needs to be part of the overall learning experience. The learned experience of mothers when nurturing their children helps teachers to establish an individualized approach which is geared towards their psychological security.

Recommendations

Anchored on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. There is still more to understand about parental resilience, particularly of the front of education and the challenges of caring for children with mental health needs. Exploring a larger sample size and utilizing focus groups would help to provide a larger variety of perspectives on the matter of care. Furthermore, a larger sample size will help provide additional grounds relating the maternal perspective of care towards their children's mental health.
2. This study briefly touched on the use of positive reinforcement, as a means of support for children with mental health needs. Thus, a study on the impact of positive reinforcement as a means of support for children with mental health needs, should be further explored as this can help understand how it affects the overall mental well-being of children. In addition, exploring other means of support for these children can help create a model which would outline, how support not just for children with mental health needs, but for all children in general, must be executed.
3. There are other themes which this study has not explored but have been implicated in the study. One of which is the role of religion in resilience. A study on the role of spiritual and/or religious resources in parental resilience needs to be explored more to understand how spirituality has helped shape resiliency.

4. One focal point in the study, is the presence of doubt, particularly when it came to their children being diagnosed. Over the recent years, outside the health care system, trust in the health care workers is always shifting, most understand that they are important in ensuring that treatment is done and followed through. However, a study on the looming doubts of parents over the health care system should be explore further. This study could help in understanding how parents react when they are given medical related news, and how this shapes the way they navigate through these.

In actuality, a lot of work needs to be done to shed light on parents' actual experiences with children who have disabilities, but through the findings gathered in the study, it can be said that in order to provide psychological security for children, particularly those with mental health needs, a personalized approach based on collaborative effort between the caregiver (i.e., mother) and the teacher should be done, as lived experiences can teach one a lot about how to approach a particular scenario in different settings for different individuals.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher obtained approval from the Dean of the School of Healthcare Professions and obtained informed consent from respondents. The study's goals, beneficiaries, and risks were disclosed, and the collected information was used for educational purposes. Respondents were informed of their voluntary participation. Confidentiality was maintained.

The study may present minimal psychological risk but may cause distress due to sensitive questions. To mitigate this, measures like psychological debriefing were taken. Respondents were concerned about privacy and confidentiality, but the researcher assured them the data was secure. Prejudice was also a concern, but these were addressed through a communication restriction assessment to ensure the data's authenticity and reliability.

The interview data was kept confidential, with no responses or participant information released without written consent. Confidentiality was ensured through informed consent and a letter page. Participants were given a code number, and access to identifying data was restricted to a limited number. Data disposal was promptly after gathering information.

Incidental findings in a qualitative study were kept confidential and stored securely. The research adviser was involved in decision-making, including sensitive topics like child

mental health stories, ensuring the study's flexibility and adherence to confidentiality standards.

The study used the Four-Dimensions Criteria (FDC) to assess rigor and trustworthiness in qualitative research. Credibility was established through prolonged engagement with participants, while transferability was achieved through diverse experiences. Dependability was achieved through a detailed description of the study's purpose and research methods. Confirmability was achieved through audio recording and notes, with clarification provided through questions as needed. This approach ensures the study's credibility and trustworthiness.

The study ensured data security by securely storing and storing the collected data. The researcher and adviser only had access to the data, with hard copies stored in a locked cabinet and digital data on a USB with a password. The researcher assessed the importance of incidental findings and consulted with advisers. Data disposal involved shredded hard copies of transcribed records, deleted digital data, and the informed consent form. Participants had the right to withdraw or withhold information after consent, and non-participation was not considered against them or others. The study's data management was carefully managed to maintain confidentiality and privacy.

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